

Synthesis and Antifungal Activities of Some New Substituted 1,2,4-Triazoles and Related Compounds

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A series of 3-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-4-aryl-5-mercapto 1,2,4-triazoles (4a-l) have been synthesised from the corresponding 1-(2,4-dichlorobenzoyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides (3a-l) by cyclization with sodium hydroxide. Methyl thioether derivatives of some of the triazoles were prepared by methylation of the mercapto groups. All the compounds were screened for their fungitoxic properties against *Alternaria tenuis* and *Curvularia verruciformis*. A few of the compounds showed good activities.

In view of the association of broad spectrum of biological activities with thiosemicarbazides and triazoles, numerous compounds containing such functions have been extensively studied¹⁻⁵. These observations prompted us to synthesise some thiosemicarbazides and triazoles incorporated with a 2,4-dichlorophenyl moiety at 3-position and their derivatives, with the objective of screening their antifungal activities against *Alternaria tenuis* and *Curvularia verruciformis*.

The 1-(2,4-dichlorobenzoyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides (3a-l) were obtained⁶ by refluxing 2,4-dichlorobenzoyl hydrazine (2) and appropriate aryl isothiocyanate in ethanol for 6-8 h. Refluxing 2,4-dichlorobenzoyl ester (1) and hydrazine hydrate (99%) in ethanol for 8 h yielded 2, m.p. 163°, requires⁷ 163-164°. Compounds 3a-k underwent cyclization to afford 3-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-4-aryl-5-mercapto 4H-1,2,4-triazoles (80-95%). The 3-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-5-mercapto 1H-1,2,4-triazole (4l) was prepared⁸ by the cyclization of 1-(2,4-dichlorobenzoyl) thiosemicarbazide (3l), (m.p. 204°) obtained by the reaction of potassium thiocyanate and conc. HCl on 2. Some of the above triazoles were methylated using methyl iodide and sodium acetate⁹.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in a Buchi oil heated apparatus and uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer 237B spectrophotometer in KBr disc. PMR spectra were determined in solvent state using tetramethylsilane as internal reference and recorded at 60 MHz on a Varian T60 spectrometer and at 90 MHz on a Varian EM 390 spectrometer.

2,4-Dichlorobenzoyl ester (1) was prepared by esterification of 2,4-dichlorobenzoyl chloride obtained

Scheme 1

ned from 2,4-dichlorobenzoic acid and thionyl chloride with absolute ethanol. 2,4-Dichlorobenzoyl hydrazine (2) was prepared following the literature⁶ method.

1-(2,4-Dichlorobenzoyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides (3a-k): To a suspension of 2 in ethanol (0.02 mol in 40 ml) was added aryl isothiocyanate (0.02 mol) and the mixture refluxed for 6 h. On cooling to room

temperature fine crystals of 1-(2,4-dichlorobenzoyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides appeared. This was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3300-3250 (NH), 1665-1575 (CONH), 1100-1090 cm^{-1} (C=S); δ (CD_2COCD_2) 9-9.5 (bs, NH).

3-(2,4-Dichlorophenyl)-4-aryl-5-mercapto-4H-1,2,4-triazoles (4a-1): 3a-k (0.07 mol) were refluxed in NaOH solution (4%, 25 ml) for 2-3 h. The resulting solution was treated with charcoal, filtered and cooled. The filtrate was acidified with dil HCl to pH 5-6. The precipitated solid after filtration was recrystallized from dilute ethanol. IR spectra were comparable with those reported in literature¹⁰, presence of strong bands in the region 1300-1100 cm^{-1} showed their existence predominantly in the thione form, but a weak band at 2600-2550 cm^{-1} also indicated their presence in the thiol form and in a tautomeric mixture¹¹ as well. Further bands near 1600 cm^{-1} showed the presence of C=N grouping of the triazole ring¹¹.

1-(2,4-Dichlorobenzoyl) thiosemicarbazide, (3l): A suspension of 2 (2.05 g, 0.01 mol), potassium thiocyanate (1.94 g, 0.02 mol), conc. hydrochloric acid (10 ml) and water (200 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. On cooling white crystals appeared. This was recrystallized from ethanol to give the product, m.p. 204°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3280 (NH), 1670 (CONH), 1125 (C=S). δ (DMSO- d_6) 9-9.5 (bs, NH), 4.6 (s, 2H).

S-Methylation of compound (4a-1): To a methanolic solution of 4a-1 (0.002 mol) fused sodium acetate (0.4 g) and methyl iodide (0.002 mol) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 4 h, cooled to room temperature, poured in crushed ice, scratched with a glass rod and kept overnight in a refrigerator. Fine colourless solid appeared, filtered, recrystallised from methanol.

The S-methylation was confirmed by the singlet at δ 2.40-2.66; but for 3-substituted 1-H-1,2,4-triazole (4l) two singlets¹¹ at δ 2.66 and 3.76 were observed confirming the methylation at both S and N protons, respectively.

The characterisation data of the compounds are presented in Table 1.

Fungitoxic activity: The synthesized compounds were screened for fungitoxic properties using the method of Horsfall and Rich¹² on two test organisms, *Curvularia verruciformis* and *Alternaria tenuis*. The test compounds were dissolved in acetone (0.1%) and 0.2 ml aliquote was taken in microscopic grooved (15 mm dia \times 3 mm deep) slides. The solvent was allowed to evaporate leaving a deposit of the test compound in the bottom of the depression and then 0.4 ml of spore suspension was taken. Suitable controls in sterilized distilled water were also used. The spore suspension was adjusted to give 40-50 conidia per low power field of microscope. The slides were incubated in moist

TABLE 1—CHARACTERIZATION DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3a-1, 4a-1 AND 5a-j

Compd. No.	- Ar	m.p. °C	Yield* %	Analysis %: Found/(Reqd.)		
				C	H	N
3a	-C ₆ H ₅	160-161	85	49.98 (49.41)	3.20 (3.24)	12.40 (12.35)
3b	-C ₆ H ₄ Br (p)	179	80	40.06 (40.00)	2.40 (2.38)	10.05 (10.00)
3c	-C ₆ H ₄ Cl (p)	170	82	44.79 (44.85)	2.60 (2.67)	11.25 (11.21)
3d	-C ₆ H ₄ Cl (o)	162	90	44.80 (44.85)	2.61 (2.67)	11.20 (11.21)
3e	-C ₆ H ₄ Cl (m)	164	89	44.79 (44.85)	2.62 (2.67)	11.22 (11.21)
3f	-C ₆ H ₄ (NO ₂) (m)	175	85	43.58 (43.63)	2.50 (2.51)	14.47 (14.64)
3g	-C ₆ H ₄ (OH ₂) (o)	145	87	50.81 (50.84)	3.60 (3.67)	11.88 (11.86)
3h	-C ₆ H ₄ (OH ₂) (p)	177	90	50.80 (50.84)	3.62 (3.67)	11.79 (11.86)
3i	-C ₆ H ₄ (OOH ₂) (o)	151	92	48.60 (48.64)	3.49 (3.51)	11.30 (11.35)
3j	-C ₆ H ₄ (OOH ₂) (p)	158	89	48.58 (48.64)	3.56 (3.51)	11.40 (11.35)
3k	-OH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	142	85	50.80 (50.84)	3.59 (3.67)	11.80 (11.86)
3l	-H	204	88	36.40 (36.36)	2.62 (2.65)	15.82 (15.90)
4a	-C ₆ H ₅	210	95	52.70 (52.17)	2.82 (2.79)	13.11 (13.04)
4b	-C ₆ H ₄ Br (p)	266	89	41.93 (41.89)	2.02 (1.99)	10.53 (10.47)
4c	-C ₆ H ₄ Cl (p)	276	94	47.05 (47.13)	2.24 (2.24)	11.76 (11.72)
4d	-C ₆ H ₄ Cl (o)	237	95	47.08 (47.13)	2.20 (2.24)	11.80 (11.72)
4e	-C ₆ H ₄ Cl (m)	198	90	47.06 (47.13)	2.28 (2.24)	11.77 (11.72)

(Table 1 contd.)

4f	-C ₆ H ₄ (NO ₂) (m)	268	80	45.71 (45.77)	2.13 (2.17)	15.30 (15.25)
4g	-C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) (o)	238	86	53.50 (53.57)	3.24 (3.27)	12.48 (12.51)
4h	-C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) (p)	201	87	53.51 (53.57)	3.22 (3.27)	12.47 (12.51)
4i	-C ₆ H ₄ (OCH ₃) (o)	260	90	51.20 (51.13)	3.09 (3.12)	11.88 (11.93)
4j	-C ₆ H ₄ (OCH ₃) (p)	206	86	51.22 (51.13)	3.16 (3.12)	11.90 (11.93)
4k	-CH ₃ - C ₆ H ₅	199-200	84	53.62 (53.57)	3.30 (3.27)	12.42 (12.50)
4l	-H	289-90	85	38.96 (39.02)	2.10 (2.03)	17.16 (17.07)
5a	-C ₆ H ₅	140-41	82	53.50 (53.57)	3.30 (3.27)	12.48 (12.50)
5b	-C ₆ H ₄ Br (p)	147-48	80	43.40 (43.37)	2.38 (2.40)	10.14 (10.12)
5c	-C ₆ H ₄ Cl (p)	129-30	78	48.56 (48.51)	2.70 (2.69)	11.89 (11.92)
5d	-C ₆ H ₄ Cl (o)	120	80	48.58 (48.51)	2.72 (2.69)	11.40 (11.92)
5e	-C ₆ H ₄ Cl (m)	132	75	48.65 (48.51)	2.73 (2.69)	11.40 (11.92)
5f	-C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) (o)	149-50	81	54.80 (54.85)	3.69 (3.71)	12.05 (12.00)
5g	-C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) (p)	135	82	54.89 (54.85)	3.68 (3.71)	12.06 (12.00)
5h	-C ₆ H ₄ (OCH ₃) (o)	151	83	52.40 (52.45)	3.51 (3.55)	11.50 (11.47)
5i	-C ₆ H ₄ (OCH ₃) (p)	105	68	52.42 (52.45)	3.49 (3.55)	11.53 (11.47)
5j	-CH ₃	114	72	43.81 (43.79)	3.22 (3.28)	15.30 (15.32)

* Of crude products.

TABLE 2—PERCENTAGE INHIBITION OF CONIDIAL GERMINATION IN THE TEST SOLUTIONS

Compounds	% Inhibition*	
	<i>C. verruciformis</i>	<i>A. tenuis</i>
3a	—	—
3b	—	—
3c	—	—
3d	—	—
3e	—	—
3g	2.49	0.56
3h	5.33	—
3i	—	—
3j	48.51	28.29
3k	100.00	100.00
4a	—	—
4b	—	—
4c	—	—
4d	43.69	19.83
4e	82.99	16.97
4f	—	—
4g	—	—
4h	46.74	40.60
4i	—	—
4j	—	—
4k	60.55	43.94
4l	19.50	24.07
5a	38.25	41.53
5b	95.75	49.58
5c	—	—
5d	—	—
5e	100.00	26.86
5f	—	—
5g	36.83	18.05
5h	18.66	6.19
5i	22.98	31.52
5j	15.61	—

* Average of four replications ; — = No inhibition.

chambers at 20-25° for a period of 24 h. The percentage of conidial inhibition was calculated by comparing the percentage germination of treated slides with the control. Average results of four replications are given in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The antifungal screening results showed (Table 2) that a few of the compounds are moderate to highly active against both the test organisms. The compound 3k, having an aryl/alkyl group showed complete inhibition of growth of both the test organisms. Among the triazole systems the compound 4e having *m*-chlorophenyl function showed enhanced activity against *Curvularia verruciformis* only.

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